
JOURNAL OF INVESTIGATIVE CRITIQUES OF
PUBLISHED SCIENTIFIC ARTICLES
VOLUME THREE, ISSUE ONE (JULY, 2021),
REPORT THREE (pp 36-46):

WHY HAS THE PAPER ENTITLED "GREATWALL-PHOSPHORYLATED α -ENDOSULFINE IS BOTH AN INHIBITOR AND A SUBSTRATE OF PP2A-B55 HETEROTRIMERS" BY WILLIAMS, M.C. ET AL. THAT WAS PUBLISHED IN ELIFE [WILLIAMS, B.C., FILTER, J.J., BLAKE-HODEK, K.A., FUDA, N.J., SHALLOWAY, D. AND GOLDBERG, M.L. (2014) ELIFE, DOI: 10.7554/ELIFE.01695] NOT BEEN RETRACTED?

Author: H.Y. Lim Tung, Ph.D., Peptide and Protein Chemistry Research Laboratory, Nacbraht Biomedical Research Institute, 3164 21st Street, Suite 122, New York City (Astoria), NY 11106, USA. E mail: hyltung2010@nacbrahtbiomedresins.net

Abstract.

The paper entitled "Greatwall-phosphorylated α -Endosulfine is both an inhibitor and a substrate of PP2A-B55 heterotrimers" authored by Williams, B.C. et al. [Williams, B.C., Filter, J.J., Blake-Hodek, K.A., Fuda, N.J., Shalloway, D. and Goldberg, M.L. and Published in the Journal eLife [eLife (2014) e01695, doi: 10.7554/elife.01695] was the subject of an investigative critique [Tung, H.Y.L. (2020) J. Invest. Cri. Pub. Sci. Articles, Vol. 1, pp193-200, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5115188]. It was previously reported that the paper by Williams, et al. was riddled with Dishonest Scientific Reported, Data Falsification and possibly Data Fabrication. After, contacting the Editor in Chief of eLife, Drs Michael B. Eisen, the author of this report was referred to the Managing Editor of eLife, Dr Wei Mun Chan who is not an expert in Enzymology by any stretch of imagination. The Managing Editor of eLife apparently obtained some response from Williams, et al. which

was not only unsatisfactory scientifically but aggravated the seriousness of this case as it was revealed that Williams et al. obtained conclusions of their paper based on some experiments in which they were counting ~3 cpm of radioactivity above background. When the author of this report pointed the fantastical results that Williams et al. claimed they were able to obtain, the author of this Report received no sign of life from the Managing editor and the Editor in Chief of eLife. This Report provides further evidence that Williams, B.C. et al. committed Dishonest Scientific Reporting, Data Falsification and Data Fabrication in their paper.

Williams, B.C. et al. published the paper entitled "Greatwall-phosphorylated α -Endosulfine is both an inhibitor and a substrate of PP2A-B55 heterotrimers" together with Filter, J.J., Blake-Hodek, K.A., Fuda, N.J., Shalloway, D. and Goldberg, M.L" in eLife [1]. In it, the authors claimed to have performed experiments that prove that a form of Protein phosphatase-2A (PP-2A) is an important and vital regulator of the activation of mitosis and meiosis. Williams, B.C. et al. [1] claimed that they could show that PP-2A (which is not an enzyme that they have any expertise of by any stretch of imagination) becomes inhibited by a phosphorylation dependent protein inhibitor termed phospho-serine 67- α -Endosulfine. They also claimed that they could show that PP-2A is also the enzyme that dephosphorylate the phosphorylation dependent inhibitor protein, which mechanistically requires a lot of imagination and some extraordinary mental gymnastic. To claim that they could show PP-2A becomes inhibited prior to the start of mitosis and meiosis, Williams, B.C. et al. [1] must first be able to determine the activity of PP-2A prior to the start of mitosis and meiosis. To claim that they can show that PP-2A is the enzyme that dephosphorylate phospho-serine 67- α -Endosulfine, Williams, B.C. et al. [1] must also demonstrate that they are able determine the activity of PP-2A using phospho-serine 67- α -Endosulfine. as substrate. It was previously demonstrated that Williams, B.C. et al. [1] (i) did not know how to assay for PP-2A and (ii) their paper contained too many fantastical results that have more to do with science fiction than science, and (iii) it was riddled with Dishonest Scientific Reporting, Data Falsification and possibly Data Fabrication [2]. After contacting the Editor in Chief of eLife, Drs Michael B. Eisen, the author of this report was referred to the Managing Editor of eLife, Dr Wei Mun Chan who is not an expert in Enzymology by any

stretch of imagination. The Managing Editor of eLife, Weil Mun Chun apparently obtained some response from Williams, B.C. et al. which was not only unsatisfactory scientifically but aggravated the seriousness of this case. The questions that must be answered are: Did Williams, B.C. et al. [1] determine the activity of PP-2A in their paper and could Williams et al. have determined the activity of PP-2A as they claimed they did? The answers to those two questions are definitely no.

In their paper, Williams, B.C. et al. [1] did not provide any information on how they were able to measure such low amount of PP-2A which has more to do with science fiction than science. In their response to the Managing Editor of eLife who is not an expert of PP-2A research or Molecular Enzymology by any stretch of imagination, Williams, B.C. et al. [1] stated that "they had to use "very hot ATP (~3000 cpm/pmol); this meant that at the lowest substrate concentration, they were adding only about 250 total cpm to the reaction. Dephosphorylation was done to about 20% of the input counts (~50 cpm) Thus the values the authors obtained were only about twice the background of ~25 cpm. The Managing Editor of eLife made the following statement to the author of this Report: "The authors knew these measurements were subject to inaccuracies because of the low inputs, but (1) they repeated these same experiments several times, and (2) they were sufficiently concerned with the K_m value that they checked it more precisely with the okadaic acid competition experiments shown in Figure 7E, where the cpm's measured were much higher. Those values were reasonably consistent between the two kinds of experiments according to the authors". The Managing Editor of eLife added that "In terms of the k_{cat} , the authors added many more total cpm to the reaction (higher substrate concentrations), and let the reactions proceed for 15 minutes or longer. In addition, they did repeated experiments to measure the k_{cat} (related to V_{max} by the amount of enzyme) with a range of experiments for varying specific activities, enzyme concentrations, and substrate concentrations, and again all the values were consistent over a ~3-fold range. It is true that the k_{cat} values appear to be lower than those you were citing for other substrates (by maybe 20-100 times, not 1.4 million times), but that was one of the points of the eLife paper". The Managing Editor of eLife also stated that "it appears that there might have been confusion on your side about amount and concentration. The figure legend states that the enzyme

concentration was $0.5 \text{ nM} = 0.5 \text{ nanoMolar}$ (rather than 0.5 nanomoles). The reaction volume was 20 microLiters , a value that can be back-calculated from the k_{cat} values in Table 1. As you will know, the value of V_{max} for a particular experiment depends on the amount of enzyme whereas k_{cat} is independent of the enzyme amount. The total amount of enzyme in the reaction was thus $\sim 1 \text{ nanogram}$. So the V_{max} would be about $50,000$ times higher than what you suggested in your note to us".

The statements of the Managing Editor of eLife show clearly that Williams, B.C. et al. [1] were making fools of the Managing Editor and Editor in Chief of eLife. Only an imbecile would state that k_{cat} is independent of enzyme amount. In order to derive the value of K_{cat} , one has to divide the value of V_{max} by the concentration of the enzyme used. It is obligatory that one has to determine the amount of enzyme used in order to determine the values of V_{max} and Enzyme concentration. If it is true that Williams, B.C. et al. [1] used 20 ul of a concentration of 0.5 nM , then there is definite proof that Williams, B.C. et al. [1] have committed Dishonest Scientific Reporting, Data Falsification and Data Fabrication. If one looks carefully at Figure 7B and 7C of the paper by Williams, B.C. et al. [1], one can see clearly that only in the realm of science fiction can one measure ~ 0.001 to 0.007 picomol of phosphatase released per min (those are the published figures). Simple arithmetic shows that Williams, B.C. et al [1] did not and could not have performed the experiments that they claim they did. With a specific radioactivity of $\sim 3000 \text{ cpm/picomol}$, one can calculate that Williams, B.C. et al. [1] were counting $\sim 3 \text{ cpm}$ or less above background. it is impossible and in the realm of science fiction to be able to count $\sim 3 \text{ cpm}$ or less above a background of $\sim 25 \text{ cpm}$. Williams, B.C. et al. [1] must explain how they were able to measure PP-2A activity of ~ 0.001 to 0.007 picomol phosphate released per min. Assaying for 15 minutes is certainly not going to help. Again, only in the realm science fiction that one would be able to measure ~ 0.001 to 0.007 picomol phosphate released per min (See Figures 7B and 7C). It is simple arithmetic. Nowhere in the paper do the authors explain how they even do the measurement. What about the linearity of the reaction? What kind of enzyme reaction Williams, B.C. et al. [1] were performing. It is quite astounding and mind-boggling that e Life would publish results in which the authors were counting $\sim 50 \text{ cpm}$ above a background of $\sim 25 \text{ cpm}$. Again, with a ^{32}P specific

radioactivity of ~3000 cpm/picomol, it is impossible and only in the realm of science fiction can one count ~50 cpm above a background of ~25 cpm. What is worse is that even the claim of being able to count ~50 cpm above a background of ~25 cpm was false. Williams, B.C. et al. [1] were in fact claiming that they could measure ~3 cpm or less above a background of ~25 cpm. The idea that one can do a PP-2A assay with total substrate radioactivity of ~250 cpm, a background of ~25 cpm and ³²P specific radioactivity of ~3000 cpm/picomol is laughable as it has to do with science fiction, and if the Managing Editor and Editor in Chief of eLife buy the idea that one can do a PP-2A assay with total substrate radioactivity of ~250 cpm, a background of ~25 cpm and ³²P specific radioactivity of ~3000 cpm/picomol, they must be real fools.

That the paper by Williams, B.C. et al. [1] contains fantastical results that has more to do with science fiction than science is an understatement. It is not clear what the reviewers and Editor in Chief of eLife were thinking when they accepted to publish the paper Williams et al. [1]. It is also not clear whether they know anything about the field of PP-2A research or Molecular Enzymology for that matter. As alluded above, the Managing Editor of eLife, knows nothing about PP-2A research and Molecular Enzymology. The author of this Report informed eLife that Williams, B.C. et al. [1] have made fools of them when they claimed that they could measure ~50 cpm of radioactivity above background of ~25 cpm when the ³²P specific radioactivity was ~3000 cpm/picomol. The above shows clearly that Williams, B.C. et al. [1] never perform the experiments that they claim they did. The data have simply been made up. Scientific Researchers who work in the laboratory with their brains and hands and are experts in the area of PP-2A research and Molecular Enzymology will know that it is in the realm of science fiction to be able to measure ~50 cpm above a background of ~25 cpm and ³²P specific radioactivity of ~3000 cpm/picomol, let alone measuring ~3 or less cpm above a background of ~25 cpm when the specific radioactivity is ~3000 cpm/picomol. It is quite a pity, disgusting and horrifying that the reviewers, Editor in Chief and Managing Editor of eLife could not determine that counting ~ 50 cpm or ~3 cpm above a background of ~ 25 cpm and ³²P specific radioactivity of ~3000 cpm/picomol is in the realm of science fiction and not science. Simple calculation of the information that was provided by Williams et al. [1] in fact shows that Williams,

B.C. et al. [1] were lying when they claimed that they could measure ~ 50 cpm above a background of ~25 cpm. The results trumpeted in Figures 7B and 7C show that Williams, B.C. et al. [1] are in fact claiming that they could measure ~3 or less cpm above a background of ~ 25 cpm.

The paper by Williams, B.C. et al. [1] concerns an important area of research in the control of the cell cycle in which it is propounded without any scientific evidence that a form of Protein phosphatase-2A (PP-2A-B55 δ) prevents mitosis or meiosis and that a protein termed α -Endosulfine/ARPP is a phosphorylation dependent inhibitor of PP-2A that becomes activated prior to entry in mitosis and meiosis [3-9]. The papers by Moshida, S. et al., Moshida, S. et al., Castilho, P.V. et al., Dupre, A. et al., Dupre, A. et al. and Dupre, A. et al. [3-9] have been shown to be suspicious as they contain many experiments that were sub-standard due to incompetence or outright Dishonest Scientific Reporting, Data Falsification and Data Fabrication [10-12]. The paper by Dupre et al. [6] was flagged by PubPeer and criticized by others to be not only substandard but also contain many instances of Dishonest Scientific Reporting and Data Falsification [10,11,13-15]. Many subsequent papers [16-26] have wrongly accepted and propounded the above thesis [1,3-9] that was arrived at through Dishonest Scientific Reporting, Data Falsification and Data Fabrication [10-12]. It must be noted that several papers have documented that cells can enter mitosis or meiosis in the absence of Greatwall kinase and ENSA/ARPP [27-33]. It is not clear why these papers are being ignored by the so-called experts and pundits, and in particular, the reviewers and Editor in Chiefs of the journals that published these papers [1,3-9,16-26]. Is it because there are no experts of cell cycle control and PP-2A research anymore. The paper by Hegarat, N. et al. [33] showed that Greatwall kinase was not necessary for mitotic entry because depletion of ENSA/ARPP-19 did not prevent mitotic entry and stated that "cells can enter prophase in the absence of cyclin B and with high PP-2A-B55 activity because depletion of Greatwall kinase or ENSA/ARPP-19 did not significantly affect the mitotic index of the depleted cells" and "quantitation of various mitotic indicators further supported the observation that cells with high PP-2A-B55 and low Cdk1-Cyclin B activity reach prophase".

The paper by Williams, et al [1] and several other papers [3-9] with dubious results and conclusions that are based on Dishonest Scientific Reporting, Data Falsification and Data Fabrication must be retracted. This is not just a scientific debate. We are talking of Dishonest Scientific Reporting, Data Falsification and Data Fabrication [2,10-12]. Many scientific hours and much money, and other resources have been wasted because it is impossible to reproduce results that can only be obtained in the realm of science fiction. eLife owes it to the scientific community to fully investigate this matter and retract the paper by Williams, et al. [1] sua sponte The Administrators of Cornell University must also investigate this matter fully and demand that the paper by Williams et al. [1] be retracted. Not retracting the paper by Williams et al. [1] shows a culture of tolerance and acceptance of Scientific Misconduct at eLife and at Cornell University that sends the wrong signal to those Scientific Researchers who work at the bench with their brains and hands to perform real experiments: At a more philosophical as well practical level, eLife and Cornell University are in effect stating that hard work does not pay but Scientific Misconduct in the form of Dishonest Scientific Reporting, Data Falsification and Data Fabrication does pay and that young Scientific Researchers must resort to Scientific Misconduct in order to able to overcome the many hurdles that they are forced to jump over. A study by Gopalakrishna, O. et al. [34] which highly mirrors previous studies [35-40] showed that a shockingly high proportion of "Scientific Researchers", including graduate students have engaged in activities associated with Dishonest Scientific Reporting, Data Falsification and Data Fabrication. It is the responsible of scientific journals like eLife to take their job seriously and to overhaul their system of peer review. On the other hand, there are many who advocate doing away with so called peer review system and let the people decide for themselves the quality and worth of a paper. With the advent of new publishing and communication technology in general, there are in fact more ways than there are journals to publish one's scientific work. Journals like eLife would not only be a laughing stock but could also become obsolete.

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On the question of reproducibility of scientific results in published scientific articles.